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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
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Liann Camille D. Perez, MAEd

Educator
Yogyakarta State University
Special Region of Yogyakarta, Indonesia
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The Eldest Daughter

The firstborn, but never the priority,
The sacrificial lamb in society,
Crushed with responsibilities and expectations
Where failure is not an option.

How can a child raise another?
Like asking a flower to bloom for two buds.
She learned to neglect herself,
Making space to accommodate someone else.

Growing up, she felt distant.
More often than not, she tried to please.
Love, to her, meant tending to needs
If not, she was unworthy.

The pain she felt was never acknowledged.
To them, the eldest must be strong.
Emotions had no space in her story,
So, she mastered the art of façade.

Years of silent cries in the dark,
Mending her own wounds,
She realized no one would save her
If she did not stand for herself.

She learned that love does not require perfection.
Flaws were never disqualifications.
The shelter she was denied
Did not make her any less.

The past must not dim or hold her back
From the sparks she is meant to have.
The only expectations she must fulfill
Are the ones born from her own truth?

To live for herself and not for the rest,
To embrace the joy she long suppressed,
To claim the dreams, she was once deprived of,
To finally take the space destined for her.